

1 **Enhanced monoaromatic hydrocarbons production via**
2 **pressurized catalytic pyrolysis of end-of-life tires**

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27 **1. Abstract**

28 One of the most active research lines in the area of end-of-life tires (ELT) recycling is pyrolysis,
29 which consists of a thermal decomposition at moderate temperatures and in absence of oxygen.
30 This process was initially focused on the recovery of carbon black and energy, this last by
31 combustion of both the gas and liquid fractions obtained. However, its rentability and alignment
32 to the circular economy goals would be improved if added-valuable chemicals were produced
33 from the pyrolytic oil. For this purpose, the application of catalysts (catalytic pyrolysis) and
34 modification of some operation conditions have been approached in previous works. However,
35 pressure has been missed until now despite the important role it may play affecting the
36 volatilization process, the vapours residence time and the pyrolytic compounds-catalyst contact.
37 This work reports for first time a comprehensive study that demonstrates that carrying out
38 catalytic pyrolysis under moderate pressure (10 bar) is very beneficial to improve the quality of
39 the oil. Thermal and ex-situ catalytic pyrolysis have been performed in a fixed-bed reactor using
40 a real scrap tire as feedstock. Both pressure and catalyst/tire ratio have been modified, using a
41 nano-crystalline ZSM-5 zeolite as catalyst. Increasing the pressure from 1 to 10 bar leads to a
42 slight reduction in the oil yield, which is somewhat more remarkable in the presence of catalyst.
43 Nevertheless, the resulting pyrolysis oil was enriched in marketable monoaromatics (benzene,
44 toluene, xylenes, ethylbenzenes and cymenes) due to a promotion of hydrogen transfer and
45 aromatization reactions. In the case of pressurized catalytic tests, there was a drastic increase in
46 the monoaromatic mass yields, reaching values up to 23-26 % and concentrations in the oil of
47 50-56 wt.%,. Finally, the feasibility to regenerate and reuse the catalyst by thermal treatment has
48 been also approached, observing minor changes in its structural and activity properties.

49

50 **Keywords**

51 End-of-life tire, pyrolysis, pressure, catalyst, ZSM-5, monoaromatics

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55 **2. Introduction**

56 Nearly 3 billion end-life tires (ELTs) are worldwide produced every year and their generation is
57 expected to rise further due to the massive and increasing demand of the transport sector. [1,2]
58 The disposal of ELTs in landfills is currently not allowed in many countries, as it produces the
59 emission of important amounts of hazardous and flammable pollutants, causing severe air, water,
60 and soil environmental contamination problems, as well as harmful effects on human health [3,4]
61 ELTs are mainly constituted of natural and synthetic rubbers (45-50 wt.%), carbon black (25-35
62 wt.%), metals and textiles (20-25 wt.%) as reinforcing materials, and minor proportions of fillers
63 (silicon dioxide and chalk), plasticizers (oils and resins) and vulcanizers agents (sulfur and zinc
64 oxide). [3,5,6] ELTs possess a calorific value of approximately 35–40 MJ/kg and a high content
65 of volatile carbon, showing huge potential for their valorization through thermochemical
66 processes. [6,7] In this sense, ELTs have been utilized as fuel for energy recovery in power plants
67 or cement kilns, but their direct combustion generates highly toxic and dangerous emissions
68 containing polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), dioxins, PMs, and SO_x.
69 Pyrolysis is considered a more environmentally friendly option than incineration for ELTs
70 valorization, as it has lower pollutant emissions and operating costs and offers a wider range of
71 value-added products. [7–9] Thus, during pyrolysis, the organic components of ELTs are
72 thermally decomposed at moderate temperatures (400-700 °C) under an oxygen-free atmosphere
73 into a gaseous fraction, a carbonaceous solid (char), and a liquid oil [8,10]. The gas phase, with a
74 significant content of methane, light olefins, paraffins, CO, and CO₂, is usually used as fuel to
75 supply the heat requirements of the process. The pyrolysis char can also be burned for energy
76 production or employed as raw material for the preparation of activated carbons and carbon black
77 fillers. [11,12] The liquid fraction (oil) is usually the main pyrolysis product as it contains valuable
78 chemicals, such as limonene, isoprene, or single ring hydrocarbons (BTXs, styrene, ethylbenzene,
79 etc). These compounds can be used, not only in fuel formulation, but also in a wide range of
80 industrial applications to obtain polymers, solvents, adhesives, dyes, pesticides, surfactants,
81 synthetic fragrances, and flavors. [13,14] The production and quality of the oil can be improved
82 by optimizing the operation conditions (i.e. temperature, heating rate, feedstock particle size, and

83 composition, etc) or by using different reactor configurations, including fixed bed, fluidized bed,
84 conical spouted bed, and rotary kiln experimental systems. [3,15–17]

85 Temperature is the most studied operating parameter in the pyrolysis of ELTs. Thus, it is well
86 established in the literature that temperatures above 450 °C are required to achieve total ELTs
87 degradation, the oil yield being maximized in the range of 500-600 °C. Temperature also
88 influences the chemical composition of the oil, promoting the conversion of aliphatic compounds,
89 such as limonene, into monoaromatic hydrocarbons. [18,19] However, in most cases, the quality
90 of tire pyrolysis oils should be increased by reducing the contents of sulfur, nitrogen, oxygen, and
91 polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) and narrowing the product distribution towards the
92 generation of valuable chemicals of industrial interest, in alignment with the circular economy
93 goals. [3,10] To this end, a wide variety of catalysts have been explored in the literature, with
94 microporous zeolites (i.e. ZSM-5, MOR, Y, and Beta, among others) being the most widely
95 investigated in catalytic pyrolysis of ELTs due to their high aromatization activity and heteroatom
96 removal capacity. [10,20–23]

97 Although extensive research has been devoted in the last decades to studying the influence of the
98 above-mentioned parameters on the pyrolysis of tire waste, very few works have evaluated the
99 effect of pressure. Nevertheless, pressure may exert influence on the volatilization of the primary
100 pyrolysis products and, consequently, on the extent of depolymerization and cracking reactions.
101 [6,24] In this sense, Ma and co-workers studied the influence of pressure and residence time on
102 the production of limonene during the pyrolysis of ELTs. [18] They found that operating under a
103 pressure of 10 bar and short residence times, the concentration of limonene in the tire pyrolysis
104 oil increased since the higher partial pressure of N₂ inhibited its decomposition. However, longer
105 residence times promoted its conversion into single aromatic hydrocarbons. On the other hand,
106 Wang et al. investigated the pressurized catalytic pyrolysis of tire sidewall rubber (SWR), using
107 hot char as catalyst, reporting an increasing trend in the production of monoaromatics when the
108 pressure was progressively increased up to 20 bar. [25]

109 These previous investigations suggest that the use of moderate pressures during the pyrolysis of
110 ELTs may be highly beneficial, allowing for increased production of valuable aliphatic and

111 monoaromatic hydrocarbons. However, none of them have explored their effect in combination
112 with the use of zeolitic catalysts, which, as mentioned above, exhibit remarkable aromatizing
113 activity. In this sense, our research group has recently demonstrated the positive effect of the
114 pressurized catalytic pyrolysis of lignocellulose over a ZSM-5 zeolite, boosting the production of
115 single-ring aromatics in comparison to the catalytic pyrolysis under atmospheric conditions. [26]
116 Taking into account these results, this work investigates for the first time, the influence of a
117 moderate increase in the operating pressure during catalytic pyrolysis of ELT using a ZSM-5
118 zeolite as a catalyst. The pyrolysis oil so obtained was particularly rich in marketable
119 monoaromatic hydrocarbons without a significant loss in the oil yield, evidencing a clear
120 beneficial effect of the use of moderate pressure in the presence of a zeolitic catalyst. In addition,
121 the regeneration and reusability of the catalyst under these conditions have been addressed in this
122 work.

123

124 **3. Materials and methods**

125 **3.1. ELTs raw sample**

126 The end-life tire waste (ELTs) used as feedstock is a steel-reinforcement-free waste provided by
127 a recycling tire company in Alicante, Spain. Before its use in the pyrolysis assays, this sample
128 was grounded with a cutting mill (Retsch SM100, Germany), sieved to a particle size of 0.5-
129 1 mm, and oven-dried at 90 °C for 48 h. The ELTs proximate analysis was carried out using a
130 Netzsch STA 449 F3 Jupiter thermobalance with a heating rate of 10 °C/min from 15 up to 900 °C
131 under inert (Ar) and air flows to determine both volatile matter and ash content, respectively. The
132 fixed carbon content was determined by difference. Ultimate analysis was performed in a Thermo
133 Scientific FLASH 2000 CHNS/O analyzer, determining the O content by difference.

134 **3.2. Catalyst characterization**

135 A commercial nanocrystalline ZSM-5 zeolite (n-ZSM-5), supplied by CLARIANT (ref.
136 HCZP90), was selected as catalyst in this work. The crystallinity of this material was evaluated
137 by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a Philips PW 3040/00 X'Pert MPD/MRD diffractometer with
138 Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$), operated at 45 kV and 40 mA (see Fig. S1 A). The textural

139 properties were determined from nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms measured at 77 K in a
140 Micromeritics Tristar analyzer. Previously, the zeolitic sample was outgassed under vacuum at
141 300 °C for 5 h. The specific surface area was calculated through the BET equation, while the
142 micropore volume and the external surface area were estimated by applying the t-plot method.
143 The total pore volume was determined at a relative pressure value of 0.97.
144 The average size of the zeolitic crystals was estimated from transmission electron microscopy
145 (TEM) images acquired by using a Philips Technai 20 Electron Microscope, operating with a
146 tungsten filament working at 200 kV. The aluminum content was measured by inductively
147 coupled plasma-optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) employing a Perkin Elmer Optima
148 7300 AD analyzer. Previously to the analyses, the sample was acidic digested using an H₂SO₄
149 and HF aqueous solution.

150 **3.2. Pyrolysis tests**

151 Pyrolysis tests were carried out in a downdraft fixed-bed reactor (400 mm length, 16 mm inner
152 diameter, made of stainless steel) that has been described in previous works. [26,27] This
153 experimental set-up is equipped with two heating sections, the thermal and catalytic ones, whose
154 temperatures can be independently monitored and controlled. These temperatures were previously
155 optimized at 600 and 450 ° C, respectively, to maximize the production of the tire pyrolysis oil.
156 In the catalytic experiments, the zeolite bed was placed in the isothermal zone of the lower heating
157 section (catalytic zone) of the reactor. Previously to the pyrolysis assays, the zeolite was
158 pelletized, crushed, and sieved into a particle size of 180 – 250 µm.

159 Typically, 4 g of dried ELTs were placed in the feedstock tank and, once the system was inertized
160 with N₂ and the targeted temperatures were stabilized, the ELTs sample was discharged into the
161 reactor using a 100 mL/min N₂ flow. Both N₂ flow and temperature were maintained for 10
162 minutes to ensure a complete reaction and collection of pyrolysis products. The resulting char
163 was accumulated in the thermal zone of the reactor, while pyrolysis vapors passed through the
164 catalytic bed – in the case of catalytic tests – and left the reactor through a system of glass
165 condensers cooled by an ice and water bath, where the oil was collected. Non-condensable gases
166 were accumulated in a totalizer for their further analysis.

167 For the pressurized pyrolysis tests, the system was modified (Fig. 1) by adding a Back Pressure
168 Regulator (BPR, GO Regulator LB1-1D01AIG111) and a pressure gauge, which allowed to
169 establish the target pressure value (10 bar). In this case, the glass condensation train was replaced
170 by a stainless-steel condenser system also cooled at 0 °C.

171

172 **Fig. 1.** Pressurized pyrolysis reactor scheme

173

174 For each pressure value (1 and 10 bar), two feedstock/zeolite mass ratios (0.2 and 0.4) were
175 evaluated. The nomenclature used for the reactions was as follows: pyrolysis mode (T is thermal
176 and C is catalytic), zeolite/ELT_{SMASS} ratios (0.2 or 0.4), if applicable, and reaction pressure (1 or
177 10 bar). Thus, the thermal experiment performed under atmospheric pressure was denoted as T-1
178 bar while, for example, the catalytic assay carried out under 10 bar using a zeolite/ELTs mass
179 ratio of 0.2 was designated as C-0.2-10 bar.

180 Regeneration and reuse of the n-ZSM-5 zeolite was also carried out after the pyrolysis tests
181 performed at both 1 and 10 bar and using a zeolite/ELT_{SMASS} ratio of 0.2. The regeneration

182 treatment consisted of a calcination in a Carbolite STF 15/450 tubular furnace at 600 °C for 300
183 minutes using an airflow of 100 mL/min.

184 **3.3. Pyrolysis products quantification and analyses**

185 Both char and oil yields were determined by weighting and referred to the mass of ELTs loaded
186 in the reactor. The volume of the gas fraction generated was calculated by subtracting the nitrogen
187 volume fed during the pyrolysis test from the total volume of gas accumulated in the totalizer.

188 The composition of the gaseous fraction was estimated by gas chromatography (GC) in an Agilent
189 Micro GC 490 equipped with two different columns, a CP-MolSieve 5 Å, and a P-PoraPLOT Q,
190 using He as carrier gas. H₂, N₂, CH₄, CO, CO₂, ethylene, ethane, H₂S, propylene, propane, 1-
191 butene, and butane were previously calibrated with standard gas mixtures to quantify their yields.

192 In the catalytic assays, the coke deposited over the catalyst was determined by thermogravimetric
193 analysis (TGA) in a Netzsch STA 449 F3 Jupiter Thermobalance burning the sample at a rate of
194 10 °C/min up to 900 °C under an airflow of 100 ml /min.

195 The CHNS-O elemental composition of both pyrolysis oil and char was estimated by triplicate in
196 a Thermo Scientific FLASH 2000 CHNS/O analyzer, measuring the content of C, H, N, and S,
197 and obtaining the O content by difference. The water content in tire pyrolysis oil was assessed by
198 Karl-Fischer titration, using a Mettler Toledo V20S Volumetric KF Titrator.

199 The oil molecular composition was obtained by gas chromatography coupled with a mass
200 spectrometer (GC-MS) in an Agilent 8860 GC equipped with an HP-5 MS column of 30 m length
201 x 0.25 mm i.d. x 0.25 mm thickness) and an Agilent 5977B MSD. The resultant chromatograms
202 were processed with the NIST EI-MS v 2.0 spectral library, and the identified compounds were
203 classified into the following families regarding their main organic functionality: aliphatic
204 hydrocarbons (AH), monoaromatic hydrocarbons (MAH), polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAH),
205 oxygenated (OC) and sulfur compounds (SC). The composition of the tire pyrolysis oils was
206 quantified by external calibration of several representative compounds of each family, including
207 limonene, toluene, p-xylene, 1,2,4-trimethylbenzene, cyclohexene, n-heptane, benzothiazole,
208 thiophene, naphthalene, and phenol, using cyclohexanol as internal standard. The mean response
209 factor of each family was used to estimate the concentration of the remaining compounds.

210 **4. Results and discussion**

211 **4.1. ELTs and catalyst characterization**

212 Both proximate and ultimate analyses of the ELTs used as feedstock in this work are shown in
213 Table 1. This feedstock exhibits a significant share of volatile components, denoting its potential
214 for their valorization via pyrolysis. The fixed carbon content is 28.5 wt.% and comes mainly from
215 the carbon black added during the tire formulation to improve their resistance to fracture and
216 abrasion. The ash percentage is in the range of those values reported in the literature, which
217 strongly depends on the additives present in the original tire and on the extent of the steel and
218 textile removal processes. [10]

219 As expected, this raw material is rich in carbon and hydrogen showing minor proportions of
220 sulfur, nitrogen, and oxygen. The presence of these heteroatoms is associated with the
221 employment of different additives during the tire formulation. Thus, sulfur and nitrogenated
222 compounds are used as vulcanizers and antioxidants, respectively, while both heteroatoms are
223 often present simultaneously in the chemicals employed as accelerators of the vulcanization
224 process. Oxygenated compounds, including oils and resins, are typically employed as plasticizers.
225 [10,28]

226

227 **Table 1.** Proximate and ultimate analyses of ELTs sample

<i>Proximate analysis (db wt.%)</i>			<i>Ultimate analysis (dab wt.%)</i>				
<i>Volatile matter</i>	<i>Fixed carbon</i>	<i>Ash</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>H</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>O</i>
64.9	28.5	6.6	87.7	7.49	0.61	1.96	2.25

228 db: dry basis, dab: Dry and ash-free basis

229

230 For the catalytic pyrolysis tests, a commercial nanocrystalline ZSM-5 zeolite (n-ZSM-5) with a
231 [Si/Al]_{MOL} of 42 (determined by ICP-OES analyses) was used as catalyst. It was selected due to
232 its excellent catalytic behavior reported in previous works of our group dedicated to the pyrolysis
233 of different kinds of organic feedstock (lignin, cellulose and hemicellulose biopolymers, real
234 lignocellulosic residues, fruit wastes, plastics, etc). [26,27,29] The main structural and textural
235 properties of this sample are included in the SI. The high crystallinity of this sample is evidenced

236 by the XRD pattern depicted in Fig. S1 A. The specific surface area is 379 m²/g, having a
237 significant contribution of the external area (Table S1) due to the nanometric size of the zeolitic
238 crystals, ranging from 30 - 50 nm, according to TEM microscopy (Fig. S1 B).

239 **4.2. ELTs pyrolysis fraction yields**

240 To study the effect of pressure and catalyst loading in the catalytic pyrolysis of ELTs, a set of
241 experiments have been carried out under pressures of 1 and 10 bar, employing zeolite/ELTs mass
242 ratios of 0.2 and 0.4 in an ex-situ configuration reaction set-up. First, Fig. 2 shows the mass yields
243 of the different pyrolysis products (char, gas, oil, and coke deposited on the zeolite surface)
244 obtained in these assays. For comparison, the yields corresponding to the thermal pyrolysis tests,
245 performed under both operating pressures in the absence of any catalyst, were also included.

246 In general, changing from 1 to 10 bar leads to a slight reduction in the oil production. Specifically,
247 the tire-derived oil yield decreases its value by 3-5 units, which may be related to the enhanced
248 generation of both gas and solid char fractions. Thus, the char yields slightly increase from 38-39
249 wt.%, in the experiments performed under atmospheric pressure, up to 39-41 wt.% operating
250 under 10 bar. These variations could be associated with the hindered volatilization of the primary
251 pyrolysis products as a result of the pressure increase, which preferentially affects the heaviest
252 compounds formed in the thermal pyrolysis zone. In addition, these heaviest compounds might
253 be adsorbed on the char generated “in-situ” and there be further transformed into more char by
254 carbonization, or into lighter compounds or gases by cracking. Similar observations in the liquid
255 and solid fraction yields have been also found in the pressurized pyrolysis of other organic wastes
256 such as lignocellulose or coal. [26,30,31].

257 In the case of the catalytic experiments using a zeolite/ELTs mass ratio of 0.2, the oil yield
258 decreases by 5-6 units in comparison to the thermal assays. This is consequence of the higher
259 generation of gases due to the catalytic promotion of secondary cracking reactions by the zeolitic
260 acid sites, as well as to the deposition of coke on the catalyst surface. However, a higher catalyst
261 loading does not induce more significant variations in the oil yield. It should be noticed that, in
262 this “ex-situ” reactor configuration, the char is generated and accumulated before the pyrolysis
263 vapors pass through the zeolitic bed, and therefore, no significant differences in the char yield are

264 observed between the thermal and both catalytic experiments. In this sense, the average ultimate
 265 analyses of the char obtained under the different operating pressures are presented in Table S2.
 266 No significant differences are observed in the elemental composition of the char with pressure,
 267 except for the oxygen content, which slightly increases in the experiments conducted at 10 bar.

268
 269 **Fig. 2.** Product distribution of ELTs thermal and catalytic pyrolysis performed at operating
 270 pressures of 1 bar and 10 bar.

271 4.3. Gaseous components

272 As mentioned and shown previously in Fig. 2, the total gas fraction yield increases working under
 273 a pressure of 10 bar, result that can be associated with the further conversion of the heaviest
 274 volatile compounds adsorbed on the char surface. In the presence of the zeolitic catalyst, this
 275 effect is more significant, since the use of higher pressure favours the adsorption and contact with
 276 the catalyst of the lightened compounds coming from the thermal reaction zone and, consequently,
 277 the promotion of secondary reactions.

278 Fig. 3 represents the mass yields of the main components of the gaseous fraction obtained in each
 279 pyrolysis reaction. It can be observed that the generation of methane (CH₄), light paraffins (LP)
 280 and Light Olefins (LO) increases when the pyrolysis pressure is rised up to 10 bar, which could
 281 suggest a higher fragmentation of side groups of large molecules. However, in the particular case
 282 of LP, their production is further boosted with the zeolite addition, whereas Light Olefins (LO)

283 decrease in a similar proportion, which could be related not only to cracking but also hydrogen
 284 transfer reactions between the compounds reaching the catalyst surface. [32] This effect is more
 285 pronounced in the experiment performed with the highest zeolite/ELTs mass ratio.
 286 The production of both molecular hydrogen and hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) is also favored under a
 287 pressure of 10 bar, suggesting the occurrence of aromatization and desulfurization processes. In
 288 the case of H₂S, it increases with the zeolite/ELTs mass ratio denoting a promotion of
 289 desulfurization reaction by the catalyst. Interestingly, although H₂ mass production is low, in
 290 terms of molar yields, is quite significant in all pyrolysis assays.

291
 292 **Fig. 3.** Yields of gaseous components from ELTs thermal and catalytic pyrolysis performed under
 293 operating pressures of 1 bar and 10 bar.

294 4.4. Chemical and molecular composition of tire pyrolysis oil.

295 In the previous section, it has been shown how the combination of moderate pressure with the
 296 utilization of ZSM-5 zeolite as catalyst affects the ELTs pyrolysis products distribution. Next,
 297 their influence on the quality of the tire-derived oil in terms of chemical and molecular
 298 compositions is discussed. In this sense, Table 2 summarizes the C, H, N, S, and O mass contents
 299 of the tire-pyrolysis oil. In addition, to show an overall picture of the effect of both parameters on
 300 the elemental composition of the oil, a Van Krevelen-type diagram is illustrated in Fig. 4, where
 301 O+N+S/C atomic ratio is represented in the X-axis. As observed, the pyrolysis oil obtained from

302 the thermal experiment at atmospheric pressure is very rich in carbon and hydrogen, with values
 303 of 85.3 and 10.6 wt.%, but still contains significant amounts of N, S, and O. The carbon
 304 percentages are somewhat improved by increasing the pressure and the catalyst loading, achieving
 305 values of ~88.8-90 wt.%. However, operating at a pressure of 10 bar, the differences observed in
 306 the carbon share with the catalyst loading are practically negligible. The hydrogen content is little
 307 affected, just showing a small reduction when working at 10 bar and utilizing a zeolite/ELTs ratio
 308 of 0.4. However, in terms of H/C atomic ratios (Fig.4), this decrease is more notable, which may
 309 denote the occurrence of dehydrogenation reactions, such as the aromatization of saturated rings.
 310 [33]

311

312 **Table 2.** Ultimate analysis of thermal and catalytic pyrolysis oils obtained under operating
 313 pressures of 1 bar and 10 bar.

<i>Pyrolysis Test</i>	<i>Ultimate analyses (daf wt.%)</i>				
	<i>C</i>	<i>H</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>O</i>
T-1 bar	85.3	10.6	1.15	1.01	1.94
T-10 bar	87.1	10.1	0.43	0.55	1.82
C-0.2-1 bar	87.4	10.5	0.40	0.73	0.97
C-0.2-10 bar	88.7	10.1	0.42	0.49	0.29
C-0.4-1 bar	88.8	9.44	0.40	0.67	0.69
C-0.4-10 bar	90.0	9.36	0.35	0.21	0.08

314

daf: dry and ash free basis

315

316 Interestingly, the change of pressure and zeolite loading differently affect the contents of N, S,
 317 and O in the oil. Thus, the use of a moderate pressure (10 bar) favors the elimination of both S
 318 and N from the oil, that is, the occurrence of both denitrification and desulfurization reactions.
 319 On the contrary, the elimination of oxygen is favored by the presence of the zeolite, and it is
 320 improved when the pressure increases, achieving almost null shares in the catalytic oil resulting
 321 from the experiment performed with a zeolite/ELTs mass ratio of 0.4 and under a pressure of 10
 322 bar. The decreasing trend of the CO and CO₂ generation with the catalyst loading and pressure
 323 (see Fig. 3), may suggest that the oxygen removal proceeds via dehydration reactions promoted

324 by the zeolite, whose catalytic effect seems to be improved by pressure. However, the water
325 generated must be completely immiscible with the oil, rich in hydrophobic components, and
326 therefore, it is not detected by Karl-Fischer titration.

327

328 **Fig. 4.** Modified Van Krevelen diagram of thermal and catalytic pyrolysis oils obtained under
329 operating pressures of 1 bar and 10 bar.

330 Although the concentration of N, S, and O is differently influenced using a higher pressure or the
331 zeolite loading, according to the Van Krevelen diagram depicted in Fig. 4, the combination of
332 both parameters produces a very positive effect in the tire pyrolysis oil composition, leading to
333 tire-derived oil with a very low concentration of heteroatoms, without a significant loss of
334 hydrogen. Of particular interest is the reaction performed at 10 bar and with a zeolite/ELTs mass
335 ratio of 0.2, which exhibits a lower proportion of heteroatoms than the experiment performed at
336 1 bar with a zeolite/ELTs mass ratio of 0.4. This fact denotes that the use of a moderate pressure
337 allows to obtain a higher quality pyrolysis oil reducing the amount of catalyst used in the reaction.

338

339 Fig. 5A shows the mass yields of the main organic families determined from the GC-MS analyses,
340 as described in the experimental section. These families have been established regarding their

341 main functionality: monoaromatic hydrocarbons (MAH), polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAH),
342 aliphatic hydrocarbons (AH), oxygenated compounds (OC) and sulfur-containing compounds
343 (SC). For a more detailed evaluation of the molecular distribution of the oil, Fig. 5B and C depict
344 the individual mass yield of the main compounds:

- 345 • Monoaromatic hydrocarbons (MAH): benzene (BEN), toluene (TOL), xylenes (XYL),
346 trimethylbenzenes (TMBs), ethylbenzene (ETB), ethylmethylbenzenes (EMBs) and
347 cymenes (CYMs). (Fig. 5B)
- 348 • Aliphatic hydrocarbons (AH): limonene, C5 and C6 cycloalkenes (C5-C6 CH), methyl-
349 butenes (Met-Butenes), isoprene and isobutylene. (Fig. 5C)

350 As observed, the thermal oil obtained under atmospheric pressure is mainly composed of aliphatic
351 hydrocarbons (9.7 wt.%, AH), such as limonene and other C5 and C6 cyclic saturated derivatives.
352 Limonene is produced by the degradation of cis-1,4-polyisoprene present in the natural rubber,
353 while C5 and C6 cyclic hydrocarbons can be produced from the isomerization and cracking of
354 limonene, as well as from the depolymerization of styrene-butadiene polymer. [19,34] The C-C
355 carbon scission of these cyclic aliphatic compounds leads to the production of isoprene and
356 isobutylene, as observed in Fig. 5C. In addition, the yield of monoaromatic derivatives (MAH),
357 mostly toluene (TOL), xylenes (XYL) and trimethylbenzenes (TMBs), is also significant,
358 achieving an overall value of 6.4 wt.%. These compounds can be formed through a sequence of
359 C-C scission, dehydrogenation, dealkylation and isomerization reactions, from limonene or other
360 cyclic hydrocarbons. [33,35] When the pressure is rised up to 10 bar, a noticeable increase in
361 MAH is produced, passing from 6.5 wt.% up to 18 wt.%. Considering the individual composition
362 of the MAH (Fig. 5 B), the higher increase is produced in BTX, alkylbenzenes, and cymenes,
363 which are high-added value compounds for fuel formulation and chemical industry. The
364 occurrence of these reactions can be also associated with the higher production of methane,
365 hydrogen and light hydrocarbons, previously discussed in Fig. 2.

366

367 **Fig. 5.** Molecular composition of thermal and catalytic pyrolysis oils obtained at 1 bar and 10 bar,
 368 in terms of mass yields, and determined by GC-MS: (A) tire pyrolysis oil families, (B)
 369 monoaromatic hydrocarbons and (C) aliphatic hydrocarbons distributions.

370 The generation of MAH is significantly boosted by the presence of the ZSM-5 zeolite, achieving
 371 yields of 13.25 and 24 wt.% for the catalyst/ELTs mass ratios of 0.2 and 0.4, respectively, working

372 at atmospheric pressure. This effect can be attributed to the catalytic conversion of limonene and
373 other cyclic hydrocarbons, via hydrogen transfer and cyclization reactions, whose presence in the
374 oil is strongly reduced in the catalytic tests (Fig. 5C). [36,37] When pyrolysis pressure is
375 augmented, the MAH yields achieve values of 23.5 and 25.8 wt.%, for the catalyst/ELTs mass
376 ratios of 0.2 and 0.4, respectively, indicating that pressure promotes the aromatization activity of
377 the zeolite due to the improved adsorption of the organic molecules over the catalyst surface. In
378 terms of concentration, these values are ca. 50-56 wt.%, denoting that the resultant oils are
379 enriched in those valuable compounds. However, this synergetic effect between pressure and the
380 catalyst is more marked when a low zeolite loading is employed since the effect of pressure seems
381 to be attenuated when using a catalyst/ELTs mass ratio of 0.4. This fact could be attributed to the
382 total consumption of limonene, which is considered the main pool to produce MAH, which
383 completely disappears in the experiments carried out with a ratio zeolite/ELTs of 0.2. In addition,
384 the formation of MAH could also be associated with the conversion of light olefins through a
385 sequence of oligomerization-cyclization and aromatization reactions, a process that is favored
386 under operating pressures higher than the atmospheric. [38]

387 On the other hand, the yield of polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), mostly alkylated naphthalenes,
388 fluorenes, and indenenes derivatives, exhibits a growing trend with the increase of pressure and the
389 catalyst loading. This fact can also be related to the promotion of cracking and decomposition of
390 oligomeric species favored by the enhanced adsorption of heavy compounds on the char surface
391 and, in the case of the catalytic experiments, the longer contact time with the zeolite catalyst.
392 These heavy compounds, present in the pyrolysis vapors, are not initially detected by GC-MS.
393 However, the promotion of cracking and depolymerization reactions, favored by the increase in
394 pressure, reduces their molecular weight, allowing their determination and quantification by this
395 technique. In this sense, Fig. 6 illustrates the yield of oil detected by GC-MS in comparison with
396 the corresponding total oil yield of each reaction. Such detected fraction yield has been estimated
397 as the sum of the individual yields of all compounds measured by GC-MS and may be used as a
398 parameter to assess the quality of the pyrolysis oil. [26,27] As observed, in the case of thermal
399 experiments, the yield of the detected fraction is much higher in the assay performed at 10 bar

400 (passing from 27.5 to 38 wt.%), indicating the presence of a higher proportion of smaller
401 molecules. These results confirm that pressure favors the decomposition of heavy oligomers into
402 light molecules, which can be subsequently processed by the zeolite, sharply increasing the
403 formation of valuable aromatic compounds. This positive effect of pressure on the yield of oil
404 detected by GC-MS is also observed in the catalytic experiments, although it is progressively
405 attenuated when the zeolite loading is larger.

406

407 **Fig. 6.** Yield of oil detected and no detected by GC-MS in thermal and catalytic pyrolysis oils
408 obtained at 1 bar and 10 bar.

409 4.5. Catalyst regeneration and reusability

410 During catalytic pyrolysis, the deactivation of the zeolitic catalyst mainly occurs due to the coke
411 deposition over the catalyst surface, blocking the zeolitic micropores and covering the acid-active
412 centers. In this sense, the potential reusability of the n-ZSM-5 in the pressurized catalytic
413 pyrolysis of ELTs was evaluated after a regeneration thermal treatment carried out under airflow
414 at 600 °C. Taking into account that the effect of pressure was more significant when working with
415 low catalyst loadings, this study was performed using a [zeolite/ELTs]_{MASS} of 0.2. Thus, Fig. 7
416 depicts the yields of oil, gas and coke of the reactions performed with both fresh and regenerated
417 zeolites under operating pressures of 1 and 10 bar (char is not included, as it was previously
418 mentioned since it is generated before the pyrolysis vapors pass through the zeolite bed and

419 therefore it is not affected by the presence of the zeolite). At atmospheric pressure, both oil and
420 gas yields were quite similar between fresh and regenerated zeolites, showing a slightly lower
421 coke generation in the latter case.

422 In the reactions carried out at 10 bar, a slightly higher yield of oil was achieved after the
423 regeneration process, which could be related to a slight loss of zeolite activity, although the
424 deposition of coke was quite similar to the pyrolysis tests performed under atmospheric pressure.
425 Accordingly, a minor generation of gases was also observed due to lower extension of cracking
426 reactions.

427

428 **Fig. 7.** Pyrolysis product distribution (oil, gas, and coke) obtained over both fresh and regenerated
429 catalysts under operating pressures of 1 and 10 bar.

430

431 The elemental composition of the tire pyrolysis oils obtained with both fresh and regenerated
432 catalysts under operating pressures of 1 and 10 bar are presented in Table 3. As observed, the C
433 and H contents of the oils obtained with the regenerated catalysts were quite similar to those
434 resulting from the experiments performed with the fresh zeolite. Just in the case of the assays
435 carried out at 10 bar, the proportions of nitrogen and sulfur were a little increased.

436

437

438

439 **Table 3.** Ultimate analysis of pyrolysis oils obtained over both fresh and regenerated catalysts
440 under operating pressures of 1 and 10 bar.

441

<i>Pyrolysis Test</i>	<i>Ultimate analyses (daf wt.%)</i>				
	<i>C</i>	<i>H</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>O</i>
C-0.2-1 bar	87.4	10.5	0.40	0.73	0.97
REG 1 bar	87.1	10.5	0.55	0.76	1.03
C-0.2-10 bar	88.7	10.1	0.42	0.49	0.29
REG 10 bar	88.1	10.3	0.60	0.71	0.27

442

daf: water and free basis

443

444 The regenerated catalysts were characterized to evaluate the impact of the pyrolysis pressure on
445 their properties (see Supplementary Information). The XRD patterns (Fig. S2) show that the
446 regenerated ZSM-5 samples preserved the main diffraction peaks of the MFI structure with a
447 similar intensity to that exhibited by the fresh sample, denoting that their crystallinity was not
448 affected by the pyrolysis pressure or by the regeneration process. Similarly, the textural properties
449 of both regenerated samples (Table S1) did not suffer significant variations, showing analogous
450 values to those exhibited by the fresh zeolite.

451 In line with the high preservation of the structural and textural properties of the zeolite after the
452 regeneration treatment, the molecular composition of the pyrolysis oils was only slightly modified
453 (Fig. 8 A). Thus, the yield of MAH only diminished about 2 units from the initial value, keeping
454 significantly higher values in the case of the experiments performed at 10 bar, suggesting that the
455 dehydrogenation and cyclization activity of the zeolite was little affected. The variations in the
456 rest of the organic families, i.e. PAH and aliphatic hydrocarbons, were even lower. Consequently,
457 the oil fraction detected by GC-MS corresponding to the experiments carried out with the
458 regenerated zeolites (Fig. 8 B) were quite similar to those obtained with the fresh samples, and
459 showing a much higher value in the case of the experiment conducted at 10 bar.

460
 461 **Fig. 8.** Molecular composition of the oils in terms of mass yields (A) and mass yields of the oil
 462 fraction detected and non-detected by GC-MS (B) obtained with both fresh and regenerated
 463 catalysts at 1 and 10 bar.

464

465 5. Conclusions

466 The role of pressure during thermal and catalytic pyrolysis of the demetallized fraction of end-of-
 467 life tires (ELT) has been assessed for first time using a fixed-bed reactor with an ex-situ
 468 configuration for catalytic assays. The comparison between reactions at two pressures (1 and 10
 469 bar) and using ZSM-5 zeolite as catalyst with two different loadings (zeolite/ELT mass ratios =
 470 0.2 and 0.4) have revealed the beneficial effect of operating at moderate pressure in terms of the
 471 quality of the pyrolytic oil obtained.

472 Changing the pressure from 1 to 10 bar in the thermal pyrolysis of scrap tires leads to a slight
473 increase in the char and gas yield due to the accumulation on the char of the heaviest compounds
474 that are then partially cracked. With the assistance of the ZSM-5 zeolite, the lightened vapours
475 coming from the thermal degradation of the tires are subjected to hydrogen transfer reactions, as
476 well as to oligomerization, cyclization and finally aromatization reactions that result in a final oil
477 with a sharp increase in valuable monoaromatics (MAH). Thus, mass yields up to 26 wt.% and in
478 concentrations up to 56 wt.% of MAHs, mainly benzene, toluene, ethylbenzenes, xylenes and
479 cymenes have been achieved at 10 bar and using a zeolite/ELTs mass ratio of 0.4.
480 Finally, as an additional indicator to validate the potential interest of applying moderate pressure
481 during the catalytic pyrolysis of ELT, it has been established that the ZSM-5 zeolite can be
482 efficiently regenerated by coke combustion, with only minor changes on its structural and activity
483 features.

484

485 **6. CRediT authorship contribution statement**

486 F.M. González-Pernas: Investigation, Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. I.
487 Moreno: Data curation, Validation, Writing – review & editing. D.P. Serrano:
488 Conceptualization, Validation, Supervision. P. Pizarro: Conceptualization, Validation,
489 Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

490

491 **7. Declaration of Competing Interest**

492 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
493 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

494

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